

50
YEARS

Edinburgh 2024

ESAT 2024

33rd European Symposium on Applied Thermodynamics

1974-2024: the 50th anniversary

Edinburgh, 9-12 June 2024

Extraction and quantification of emerging pollutants in environmental water

Didier M. Rodríguez, María C. Naranjo, Maria João Nunes, João M. M. Araújo and Ana B. Pereiro*

LAQV, REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

*e-mail: anab@fct.unl.pt

Emerging pollutants (EPS) are substances generated mainly by human activities, which are released into the environment and for which no environmental regulations have been defined [1]. Two of the major groups of EPSs are pharmaceutical residues and per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). These EPS play a vital role and are widely used in industry, but once excreted they can become highly toxic in ecosystems, and even bioaccumulative. PFAS are highly persistent and bioaccumulated in air, water and soil, and together with pharmaceutical residues, generate serious contamination of land, effluents, surface water, groundwater and oceans, being detectable in drinking water and even rainwater. Bioaccumulation in humans increases the risk of developing cancer, hepatic and immune disorders, as well as birth defects. Reliable analytical methods and toxicity assessment methods are the basis for the management or elimination of EPS. This work describes the development of a method for the extraction, purification and quantification of pharmaceutical and PFAS contained in aqueous matrices, evaluating the limits of detection and quantification using the versatility of the UHPLC MSMS system. For the method development, each analyte was tested separately (3 pharmaceutical compounds and 3 PFAS compounds and their respective internal standards) and then the method was optimized for a mixture of the analytes in a synthetic aqueous matrix. The SPE (Solid Phase Extraction) method was optimized and validated for the extraction and purification step, at different volumes and concentrations of the analytes. Finally, the extraction and quantification methods are validated on real samples in different environment aqueous matrices and will also be used as a method for quantification and verification of the effectiveness of different EPS adsorption and removal treatments.